

Largest wildfires in Angola: Correlation of Vegetation and Meteorological Variables with Wildfire Intensity

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Abstract

Wildfires have significant impacts on biodiversity and their effects have been exacerbated in recent times by global warming. In the present study, we investigated the relationship between wildfire intensity and meteorological variables as a function of vegetation type in Angola, focusing on the largest wildfires in 2020. We used the Globfire, MODIS Surface Reflectance, ERA5-Land, and CHIRPS data to analyze wildfire severity measured by its differenced normalized burn ratio (dNBR), duration, and burnt area, and their correlations with normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), temperature, precipitation, and wind speed. Our results show significant positive correlations between all measures of fire severity. In general, wildfire severity was positively correlated with pre-fire NDVI and, except for forests, negatively correlated with wind speed. Future studies can build on these results to develop predictive models for mitigation and rapid response to wildfires.

Introduction

Wildfires pose significant risks to life (Di Virgilio et al., 2019) and have considerable economic, social, and environmental impacts (Bowman et al., 2017). Africa is by far the most affected continent, with around 70% of the global burnt areas (Van der Werf et al., 2010). According to the sixth IPCC Assessment Report, over the last century, climate conditions promoting wildfires have become more probable and will likely be more frequent at higher levels of global warming in some regions (Ranasinghe et al., 2021). Considering the urgent need for wildfire adaptation and mitigation strategies, it is imperative to identify the factors that contribute to wildfire intensity.

Pre-wildfire vegetation health and density of a region, colloquially referred to as its "greenness", is a potential candidate. It can be assessed through the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), a commonly employed metric for screening vegetation diversity and tracking its dynamics, such as those arising from seasonal changes or extreme weather events (Pettorelli et al., 2005). For instance, one previous study (Mbatha and Xulu, 2018) reported a strong negative correlation between pre-fire NDVI and burned area index. Similarly, meteorological variables such as temperature, precipitation and wind speed are known to have the potential to influence wildfire intensity. For example, high air temperatures and lack of precipitation can favour wildfires (Tošić et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 2022). Additionally, higher wind speeds are associated with larger fire spreads (Beer, 1991).

Here, we investigated the relationship between vegetation and meteorological variables with wildfire intensity. We defined wildfire intensity as an umbrella term that encompasses wildfire duration, burnt area, and severity (measured in terms of the differenced Normalized Burnt Ratio (dNBR)). This analysis was restricted temporal and spatially, focusing on the largest wildfires in 2020 in Angola, a country with one of the highest numbers of wildfires per year (Artés et al., 2019). While Angola encompasses a diversity of vegetation types, most wildfires

during 2020 burned forests, herbaceous vegetation and shrubs (Figure 1A), and therefore, our study was limited to those.

Data

To obtain data for our variables of interest, we collected data from four datasets: 1) Globfire, a subset of the Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS) including the MODIS burned area product (Artés et al., 2019); 2) MODIS Surface Reflectance 8-Day product (Vermote, 2021); 3) ERA5-Land (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) for temperature and wind data; and 4) CHIRPS for precipitation (Funk, 2015).

Methods

First, using the Globfire dataset, a subset of the Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS) which provides descriptive information about wildfires (Artés et al., 2019), we selected 50 largest wildfires per vegetation type for the most affected vegetation types (forest, shrubs and herbaceous vegetation) in Angola in 2020 (Figure 1B) and collected their burnt area and fire duration. Then, using satellite images from the MODIS Surface Reflectance 8-Day product (Vermote, 2021) we calculated 1) the pre-fire NDVI for each of the selected fires and 2) estimated wildfire severity by calculating the dNBR (Figure 1D). Finally, we used ERA5-Land (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) and CHIRPS datasets (Funk, 2015) to collect monthly temperature, precipitation and wind data during the period of each fire. For all variables, we averaged over space – that is, the rectangle including the entire spatial extent of the wildfire, based on its minimum and maximum values of longitude and latitude (Figure 1C) - and time, obtaining one value per variable for each fire.

Afterwards, we performed pairwise correlations to determine the relationship between a vegetation parameter (NDVI), different meteorological variables (temperature, precipitation and wind speed) and wildfire intensity (dNBR, fire duration, burnt area) (Figure 1E). The analysis was performed separately on fires of different vegetation types in order to understand the influence of vegetation type on these variables and their relationships.

We observed multiple significant ($p < 0.05$) positive and negative correlations between these variables (Figure 1E,F). First, for forests and herbaceous vegetation, there was a positive correlation between all three variables pertaining to wildfire intensity, i.e., burnt area, fire duration, and dNBR, showing that longer and more severe fires are associated with more burnt area. For shrubs, we only observed a positive correlation between burnt area and fire duration. Second, pre-fire NDVI correlated positively with dNBR for all vegetation types and correlated positively with burnt area for forests and with fire duration for herbaceous vegetation. This is in line with a previous study (Catarino et al., 2020) and suggests that areas with denser vegetation cover are more favourable for creating severe and in certain cases, large and long-lasting fires. However, this contrasts with a negative correlation reported previously (Mbatha and Xulu, 2018) and may depend on climatic conditions in the specific area such as vegetation moisture. For the meteorological variables, we observed that wind speed was correlated negatively with dNBR for herbaceous vegetation, and with fire duration for shrubs and herbaceous vegetation, suggesting that for smaller vegetation, fires are shorter and less severe when wind speed is high, potentially because of quicker fuel consumption. Finally, temperature and wind speed were negatively correlated for all types of vegetation, which goes in line with previous findings that windy days are colder than non-windy ones.

Figure 1: The relationship between vegetation, meteorological variables and fire intensity in Angola. **A.** The distribution of wildfires in Angola in 2020 by vegetation type. The most affected vegetation type is forests, followed by herbaceous vegetation and shrubs. **B.** The spatial distribution of the largest fires in Angola and their vegetation type. Most forest fires occur in the East and the South, while most herbaceous vegetation fires occur in the North-East. **C.** Illustration of the methodology. For each fire of interest, we selected the rectangle corresponding to its extent, based on its minimum and maximum values of longitude and latitude, and collected temperature, precipitation, wind, NDVI and dNBR values for that area. **D.** Example pre-fire NDVI (left) and dNBR values (right) derived from satellite images obtained from the MODIS product. The images depict the vegetation and burn severity indices for one of the largest fires of Angola. **E.** Correlation matrices for each vegetation type. The highest positive correlations are between burnt area and fire duration; dNBR and burnt area; and dNBR and pre-fire NDVI. Only significant correlations are shown ($p < 0.05$). **F.** Scatterplots of the highest positive correlations for forest fires.

Conclusion

Overall, we showed that the intensity of wildfires in Angola, i.e., their severity, duration and area, is influenced by certain vegetation factors such as NDVI (i.e., “greenness”), as well as by meteorological variables such as wind speed. Our results suggest that we can use different vegetation and meteorological variables to identify areas more prone to intense wildfires. Further research is needed to combine these different variables in predictive models in order to mitigate wildfires and respond to them as quickly as possible.

Figure 2: Summary of correlations between vegetation, meteorological and wildfire variables.

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